

WORKSHOP #4

Sustainable practices: bycatch
reduction and marine conservation

Workshop Brief

The fourth participatory workshop is entitled ‘Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation’ and aims to raise awareness about the incidental capture of non-target species, particularly sensitive endangered species (such as sea turtles, marine mammals, seabirds, sharks, sponges and corals). The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Raise awareness among fishers about the importance of reducing bycatch in fishing.
- Familiarise participants with various devices and techniques used to minimise bycatch.
- Provide guidelines and best practices for acting in case of bycatch.
- Promote the adoption of sustainable practices that benefit the health of marine ecosystems.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately two hours (see the proposed agenda).

Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet, two Informed Consent Forms, and the Feedback form. Participants are asked to sign the presence list and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome (*plenary*)

| 10 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. Finally, the participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 1: Species commonly captured (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Participants in each group start by nominating a spokesperson to present the results at the plenary sessions. A facilitated open discussion is encouraged so participants share their bycatch experiences. Then, participants are asked to:

- Identify non-target species commonly captured,
- Rank these species based on capture frequency,

- Associate captured species with the specific fishing gear used,
- Identify endangered species among the captured ones.

Printed cards with images of common bycatch species (e.g. seabirds, marine mammals, turtles, sharks, sponges and corals) are provided to support the exercise. Once a consensus is reached, participants write their answers on the exercise sheet (Figure 1).

Exercise 1: Based on your experience, register the species commonly involved in bycatch, link them to the fishing gears, identify the endangered species

BYCATCH SPECIES PER FISHING GEAR

BYCATCH SPECIES:

more captured

FISHING GEAR:

less captured

ENDANGERED SPECIES

Exercise 1 | Group _____
Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] .
[dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 1. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #4)

Exercise 2: Best practices to reduce bycatch (group)

| 20 minutes

In the second exercise, participants are asked to deliberate on the practicality and applicability of best practices. To facilitate the conversation, a table summarising available best practices for reducing bycatch will be provided. Participants are asked to i) identify the most suitable practices for their needs (given the fishing gear used and common bycatch species), ii) discuss ways of implementing them on board, and iii) discuss major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. Key conclusions drawn from this discussion should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 2).

Exercise 2: Based on your experience, which measures can you adopt to reduce bycatch?

MINIMISATION MEASURES	SWOT ANALYSIS
<p>MEASURES TO REDUCE BYCATCH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ <p>HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE SELECTED MEASURES?</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>STRENGTHS (what you're good at)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>THREATS (risks or challenges)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>

Exercise 2 | Group _____
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] .
 [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 2. Example of the second exercise sheet (workshop #4)

Exercise 3: Protocols in case of bycatch (group)

| 20 minutes

In the third exercise, participants are asked to deliberate on i) the rapid response protocols and on-board handling practices in case of bycatch, ii) the importance of communicating and notifying the relevant authorities, as well as iii) major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. The discussion should extend to methods of implementing these protocols/practices. Key conclusions drawn from this discussion should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 3).

Exercise 4: Dissemination and leadership (group)

| 20 minutes

In the final exercise, participants are asked to propose methods for disseminating best practices to fellow fishers, and to identify either individual fishers, vessels or communities that demonstrate leadership and social influence in terms of supporting innovation and sustainable behaviours relating to the adoption of sustainable practices. The main conclusions should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 4).

Exercise 3: Based on your experience, how do you handle bycatch and which protocols /best practices can you adopt in case of bycatch?

BEST PRACTICES/ PROTOCOLS

COMMON PRACTICES IN CASE OF BYCATCH:

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

NOTIFICATION (competent authorities, other):

.....

.....

ARE THERE IMPLEMENTED PROTOCOLS?

YES NO IF YES, WHICH?

SUGGESTIONS:

.....

.....

.....

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

.....

.....

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

.....

.....

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

.....

.....

THREATS (risks or challenges)

.....

.....

Exercise 3 | Group
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 3. Example of the third exercise sheet (workshop #4)

Exercise 4: Write suggestions to disseminate information and encourage other fishers to adopt similar practices.

SPREAD THE WORD

suggest ways of disseminating best practices to fellow fishers

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LEADERSHIP

identify either individual fishers, vessels or communities that demonstrate leadership and social influence

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Exercise 4 | Group
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 4. Example of the fourth exercise sheet (workshop #4)

Presentation of results & discussion (*plenary*)

| 20 minutes

Following the exercises, participants convene in the plenary session to share and deliberate on the outcomes. Each group's spokesperson displays the exercise sheets and presents the group's findings. A discussion among participants is encouraged and, at the end, moderators provide a summary of the suggestions put forth by all groups.

Workshop final conclusions (*plenary*)

| 10 minutes

The workshop concludes with the presentation of final conclusions, encouraging participants to share additional insights or address any lingering questions. Participants are invited to complete the feedback form and to leave it at the registration table.

Resources and materials

A set of materials will be available to participants at the group tables to fulfil the workshop exercises, namely:

- Printed cards with images of the most common bycatch species,
- One A4 table per group summarising existing solutions to reduce bycatch,
- Four exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed,
- Colourful pens.

In case partners decide to provide a theoretical background on the bycatch theme, the seminar slides corresponding to workshop 4 can be used.

WORKSHOP #4

Sustainable practices: bycatch
reduction and marine conservation

Resources

4th WORKSHOP

Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| 13:45 - 14:00 | Registration |
| 14:00 - 14:10 | Welcome |
| 14:10 - 14:30 | Exercise 1: Species commonly captured |
| 14:30 - 14:50 | Exercise 2: Best practices to reduce bycatch |
| 14:50 - 15:10 | Exercise 3: Protocols in case of bycatch |
| 15:10 - 15:30 | Exercise 4: Dissemination and leadership |
| 15:30 - 15:50 | Presentation of results & discussion |
| 15:50 - 16:00 | Workshop final conclusions |
| 16:00 - 16:20 | Coffee break |

Feedback Form

We ask you to take a moment to provide your feedback on the workshop. Your responses will be used to improve future NETTAG+ workshops.

Name (optional): _____

On a scale of 1 to 4 where 1 is strongly disagree and 4 is strongly agree, please circle the most appropriate answer:

1. The Workshop venue was:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Comfortable | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Well located | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Food and refreshments were adequate | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

2. The Workshop content was:

- | | | | | |
|-----------------------|---|---|---|---|
| a) Relevant | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Comprehensive | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Easy to understand | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

3. The Workshop was:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Well paced | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Breaks were sufficient | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) A good mix between listening and activities | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

4. The facilitators were:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Knowledgeable | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Well-prepared | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Responsive to participant's questions | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

5. What did you like best about this Workshop?

6. What did you like least about this Workshop?

Thank you for participating, we appreciate your feedback.

Background information on bycatch

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Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA).

Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Indicate the place | indicate the date dd/mm/yyyy

Bycatch

- Bycatch encompasses **unintentional captures** during fishing operations, extending beyond target species
- **Trawl, longline, and gillnet** have the highest bycatch rates
- **Major threat to marine vulnerable species:** sea turtles, seabirds, elasmobranchs, marine mammals, corals, and sponges
- Also impact fisheries' profitability and sustainability

Bycatch of Marine Megafauna

- Marine megafauna (seabirds, turtles, cetaceans and elasmobranchs): characterized by longevity, slow growth, low fecundity, delayed sexual maturity, and extensive mobility.
- Bycatch is the leading cause of human-induced mortality in marine megafauna.
- These traits make them particularly sensitive to added mortality, often compromising population viability.

REDUCE project: Reducing the bycatch of threatened megafauna in the East Central Atlantic Ocean

REDUCE Working area and fishing fleets

INDUSTRIAL PELAGIC FISHERIES (PURSE SEINE, LONGLINE AND TRAWLER FISHERIES)
LONG-DISTANCE EUROPEAN FISHERIES

Purse seine

Longline

Trawler

Designed by David March

Fishing effort (h)

REDUCE project aims to gather the efforts of all sectors involved in bycatch to REDUCE bycatch of Marine Megafauna in East Central Atlantic

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union

REDUCING THE BYCATCH OF THREATENED MEGAFUNA IN THE EAST CENTRAL ATLANTIC OCEAN

Grant Agreement ID 101135583

€ 8.156.593,75 EU Contribution

JAN 2024 DEC 2027

Funded under Food, Bioeconomy Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment

COORDINATED BY

PARTNERS

ASSOCIATED PARTNERS

Seabirds

- Seabirds are at risk of entanglement in various fishing gears, including longlines, trawls, and nets
- An estimated 200,000 seabirds suffer accidental fatalities annually in Europe due to interactions with fishing gear
- Seabirds, attracted to bait used by anglers, often fall victim to hooks and entanglement in fishing lines
- Diverse feeding habits, including surface and deep diving, increase the vulnerability of seabirds to fishing gear interactions

BirdLife International; NOAA

How bycatch occurs

BirdLife International: https://youtu.be/0_a3oXbfsXo

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Making fisheries safe for seabirds

BirdLife International: https://youtu.be/YGK_1xAZiWQ

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Gillnet bycatch minimisation measures:

- **'Scary bird device'**: Simulates a predator (eagle or falcon) driving birds away from the area of the fishing operation
- **Night settings**: When seabird activity is reduced
- Proper net cleaning and disposal of discards outside of fishing periods: Minimise attraction to birds
- Increased net visibility: Add high-visibility mesh to the top of the net or LED lights
- Increased net depth

Longline bycatch minimisation measures:

- **'Scary bird device'**: Simulates a predator (eagle or falcon) presence to deter birds
- **'Bird scaring lines' or tori lines**: Colourful streamers, to deter birds from the stern of the vessel
- Setting of nets/lines at night: To avoid peak seabird feeding times
- Weighted Lines: To increase baited hooks' sink rate, reducing bird snag risk

Trawl bycatch minimisation measures:

- **Tori lines**
- Night settings

Making fisheries safe for seabirds

- Examples of bird-scaring lines or tori lines

Video: <https://vimeo.com/709031744>

Video: <https://youtu.be/szNQpQzETK4?feature=shared>

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Sea turtles

- Sea turtles have survived for more than 200 million years
- There are 7 recognised species in the world
- In Europe, turtles are primarily found in the Mediterranean Sea
- Turtles are **migratory** species; they take **20-30 years to mature** and can **live longer than 100 years**
- Turtles have an important role in the ecosystems maintenance and reflect marine environmental health
- 6 out of the 7 are listed as vulnerable, endangered, or critically endangered on the IUCN Red List

-> Nesting populations in the Mediterranean

-> Largest species of turtle
-> Occasional visitor of the Mediterranean and NE Atlantic

Source: [WISE MARINE](#); [MEDASSET](#); [WWF 2022](#).

Sea turtles

- Bycatch poses a significant threat to all species of marine turtles globally, leading to hundreds of thousands of deaths annually
- Turtles are **air-breathers** and can drown if submerged for long, as it can happen when captured by trawl or set nets
- Turtles incidentally captured by longlines are usually released alive, but many will die, mainly for the ingested line
- Simple **onboard best practices** that can reduce the high mortality of captured turtles:
 - Keep any turtle apparently dead or very weak on the deck until they become active again
 - Cut the line very close to the mouth

Source: [EuroTurtles](#); [WWF 2022](#).

Making fisheries safe for sea turtles

Turtle Excluder Device (TED)

- a grid which diverts marine turtles and other large marine fauna out of a trawl net, already used in tropical shrimp trawls

Source: [WWF 2022](#).

Video: <https://youtu.be/jyhumLE7B40>

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Sharks

Adapted from: Artwork by Jamy Silver © Save Our Seas Foundation

WHY ARE SHARKS IMPORTANT?

Across the world's oceans, there are over **500 species** of shark.

Whale shark

Goblin shark

They have inhabited our oceans for over **400 million years.**

Basking shark

Zebra shark

Tiger shark

Angel shark

Catshark

Scalloped hammerhead

Blue shark

Bonnethead

Epaulette shark

Some are **top predators**, others are the **clean-up crew** of the ocean.

Their diverse roles are part of a balance needed for **healthy oceans.**

Sharks

Adapted from: Artwork by Jamy Silver © Save Our Seas Foundation

WHY ARE SHARKS IMPORTANT?

Losing sharks can disrupt the **delicate ecosystem balance** that they help maintain.

As many as **100 million** sharks may be killed every year in commercial fisheries.

Many shark populations have **declined by more than 90%**, due to overfishing, climate change and habitat loss.

Our future depends the oceans.

The ripple effects of an ocean without sharks are complex and potentially devastating.

Marine mammals

- Marine mammals play crucial ecological roles and are indicators of marine ecosystem health
- They are generally **highly mobile**, possess **large body sizes**, and have **low reproductive rates**
- Which makes them **vulnerable** to human-related stressors
- The disappearance of large predators (e.g. dolphins) has a wider impact on the environment and marine resources
- Bycatch/entanglement in fishing gear poses the **greatest threat** to marine mammal species globally
- Although it's **illegal** to catch marine mammals
- Over 600,000 marine mammals are accidentally captured each year worldwide

BOTTLENOSE DOLPHIN

© M. Camm

LONG-FINNED PILOT WHALE

© M. Camm

GRAY SEAL

NOAA Fisheries

Source: [FAO](#); [CETAMBICION project](#)

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Marine mammals

Why bycatch happens?

- Same fishing area or target species (trophic competition)
- Attracting dolphins near fishing boats (depredation)
- Lack of visibility/selectivity of some fishing gear that accidentally catches non-target animals

Source: [CETAMBICION project](#)

Marine mammals bycatch mitigation

- Improving the visibility of fishing gear
 - ✓ Active or passive acoustic deterrents
 - ✓ Acoustic reflectors
 - ✓ Informative warning signal (DOLPHINFREE project)
 - ✓ Change of net colour
 - ✓ Lighting of nets
- Modification of fishing gear
 - ✓ Modification of the nets
 - ✓ Trawl exclusion system
 - ✓ "Intelligent" fishing gear
- Changes in fishing practices
 - ✓ Alternative fishing gear
 - ✓ Duration and period of immersion of the fishing gear
 - ✓ Depth of the net (2-4m below surface)
 - ✓ Adoption of good practice
- Fishing effort limitation and management
 - ✓ Time and space closure
 - ✓ Area closure based on reaching a catch limit
 - ✓ "Move-on" rule
 - ✓ Predictive fisheries management
- Regulatory and incentive measures
 - ✓ Regulation, Monitoring and surveillance
 - ✓ Economic levers

Source: [CETAMBICION project](#)

Acoustic Deterrent Devices - 'pingers'

Excluder Device

Backdown procedure

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Source: UNEP/CMS & WWF, 2020. Guidelines for the safe and humane handling and release of bycaught small cetaceans from fishing gear.

FISHING GEAR INNOVATIONS DESIGNED TO LOWER THE RISK OF ENTANGLEMENT FOR LARGE WHALES

Adapted from whale illustrations
© Parks Canada

DEPLOY FISHING GEAR MADE OF COMPONENTS WITH A LOW BREAKING STRENGTH

The use of polyethylene, time-tension line cutters or plastic links, for example, offers a breaking strength of 770 kg or less, which makes it easier to release an entangled animal

USE A MAXIMUM ROPE DIAMETER OF 16 mm

Too large a diameter increases the breaking strength and complicates the release of an entangled animal, while excessively thin rope (6 mm) can lead to more severe skin injuries

USE ROPELESS GEAR

Technologies include various types of remote triggering devices and GPS positioning and recovery systems in order to eliminate the need for vertical lines

REDUCE FLOATING ROPE ON WATER SURFACE

Adopt good fishing practices to reduce floating rope such as rope shot, Inflatable lift bag or simply properly coiling one's rope

USE SINKING ROPE BETWEEN TRAPS OR POTS

Sinking rope helps limit the amount of rope floating above the seafloor

AVOID USING SINGLE-POT GEAR

Traps or pots can be deployed in series to reduce the number of buoys and the amount of rope used

Safe handling and release

- Maximises survival chances of bycatch species after interaction with fishing gear
- Includes best practice methods and vessel manoeuvres to avoid taking bycatch species
- In purse seine operations, bycatch can be released from the net whilst in the water or released once brought on deck
- With line fishing operations bycatch may either be released from the side of the vessel or after being brought on board
- There are safe handling and release guides for different species and fishing gear

Source: [BMIS](#)

Let's clean up the ocean together!

Thank you for your attention

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Workshop #4

A3 exercise sheets

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Exercise 1: Based on your experience, register the species commonly involved in bycatch, link them to the fishing gears, identify the endangered species

BYCATCH SPECIES PER FISHING GEAR

BYCATCH SPECIES:

FISHING GEAR:

more captured

less captured

- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓

ENDANGERED SPECIES

Exercise 1 | Group _____

Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | *[add the location of the workshop]*,
[dd/mm/yyyy]

Exercise 2: Based on your experience, which measures can you adopt to reduce bycatch?

MINIMISATION MEASURES

MEASURES TO REDUCE BYCATCH

- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓

HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE SELECTED MEASURES?

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 2 | Group _____

Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | *[add the location of the workshop]*,
[dd/mm/yyyy]

Exercise 3: Based on your experience, how do you handle bycatch and which protocols /best practices can you adopt in case of bycatch?

BEST PRACTICES/ PROTOCOLS

COMMON PRACTICES IN CASE OF BYCATCH:

NOTIFICATION (competent authorities, other):

ARE THERE IMPLEMENTED PROTOCOLS?

YES NO IF YES, WHICH? _____

SUGGESTIONS:

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 3 | Group _____

Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | *[add the location of the workshop]*,
[dd/mm/yyyy]

Workshop #4

Cards: bycatch species

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Photo by Jonny Gios on Unsplash

SEABIRDS

Photo by NOAA on Unsplash

MARINE MAMMALS

Photo by David Clode on Unsplash

SHARKS

©Kostas Papafitsoros

SEA TURTLES

Photo by Quite Retro on Unsplash

SPONGES

Medi Ambient. Generalitat de Catalunya / Flickr

CORALS

Workshop #4

List of Bycatch Solutions

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GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE					BYCATCH SPECIES			
		 Seabirds								
Acoustic Pingers	Acoustic pingers serve as a marine mammal deterrent device in net fisheries by emitting a sound that can be detected within a certain distance of the net. Implementation of acoustic pingers in gillnet fisheries has become widespread over the last decade, especially in the northern Atlantic, where it is required by law in numerous fisheries.	✓					✓			
Avoid Hotspots	Hotspots are areas that have a higher abundance of bycatch taxa where it is more likely to have high bycatch rates if fishing is conducted. It is a best practice to avoid setting fishing gear in these locations.	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Backdown Method	The backdown method is conducted after setting the purse seine net but before finishing the haul. This process creates a channel and an opening at the back of the net where non-target species (especially small cetaceans and sea turtles) can escape at the surface.					✓	✓	✓	✓	
Bird scaring devices	Shaped like a small eagle or hawk, the kite simulates the presence of a predator, driving the birds away from the fishing area. To maximise its effectiveness, it should be combined with other measures.	✓	✓		✓					✓
Circle Hooks	In circle hooks, the pointed tip is bent back towards the shaft decreasing the spacing between the sharpened tip and shaft and changing the hook angle. The shape of the circle hook makes it harder for ETP bycatch to get hooked due to differences in jaw morphologies, but doesn't impact catch rates in fish and can even in some cases increase catch rates.		✓				✓	✓		
Decreased Soak Times	Soak time is the amount of time that deployed fishing gear stays in the water. The longer the gear is set in the water, the higher the bycatch rate will be.	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE					BYCATCH SPECIES			
		 Seabirds								
Excluder Devices	Excluder devices are modifications to trawl nets that block specific taxa from getting dragged into the cod end of the net and allows them to swim out while the trawl net is being towed. Excluder devices are effective and being used in trawl fisheries that interact with bottlenose dolphins, common dolphins, seals, and turtles, for example.				✓		✓	✓		
Hook Shielding Devices	A hook shielding device encases or covers the tip of the baited hook during the longline set to prevent predation by seabirds. The shielding devices is designed to then open or release the hook at a specified depth below which seabirds can dive.		✓							✓
Jelly FAD	Jelly FADs are non-entangling biodegradable fish aggregating devices that have proven to be just as effective as traditional FADs at aggregating targeted fish species. Due to their structure design and materials used, they do not pose an entanglement risk to sea turtles, dolphins/porpoises, and sharks/rays, and if lost will biodegrade much faster than traditional FADs.					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Management of offal and discards	Birds are attracted to fishing vessels to feed on processing waste and discarded fish. To reduce this attraction, effective waste management is crucial: i) retain waste onboard during trips. If impracticable, avoid discharge during fishing activity; ii) where retention of waste is impracticable, convert offal into fish meal and restrict discharge to liquid only; iii) where meal production and retention are impracticable, temporally store waste for at least two hours before controlled discharge it in batches; iv) if other methods aren't feasible, reduce waste to smaller particles. Efforts should be made to eliminate or limit offal discharge during active fishing periods.		✓		✓					✓
Modified Purse Seine	Modified purse seines were developed to address seabird bycatch in the Chilean anchovy and sardine purse seine fisheries. Specific modifications include moving the locations of the buoys					✓				✓

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE					BYCATCH SPECIES			
		 Seabirds								
	and decreasing the amount of excess netting. The implementation of the modified purse seine resulted in a 98% decrease in seabird bycatch rates for vessels with an increase in target catch.									
Net Lights	Net lights are LED lights attached directly to fishing nets, most commonly in gillnet fisheries, that serve to illuminate the top of the net making it more noticeable to bycatch.	✓					✓	✓		
Night Settings	Seabirds are visual hunters and most active during daylight hours. By shifting to setting fishing gear when it is dark, seabird interaction with baited hooks and nets is greatly reduced thereby decreasing bycatch rates.	✓	✓		✓				✓	
Non-Dolphin/Whale Shark Sets	Dolphins/porpoises and whale sharks are often found with target fish in the open ocean, and were often used as an indication of where to set purse seine nets. This led to large bycatch rates for both in historical purse seine fisheries leading to very high mortality rates.					✓	✓		✓	
Non-Entangling Biodegradable FAD	Fish aggregation devices (FADs) are structures that attract target fish, normally tuna, which are used to increase fishing efficiency. Nets and ropes that attach to the main structure and hang in the water often entangle non-target species such as sea turtles, seabirds, and sharks that are also attracted to the FAD.					✓	✓	✓	✓	
Non-Steel Leaders	Leaders are a segment of the branch line that the baited hook is directly attached to. For fisheries that do not retain sharks, it is recommended to use a leader material that can be cut, allowing sharks to break off in the water, or be cut from the main line by the crew when hauling.		✓						✓	
Ropeless (On-Demand) Pot/Trap Systems	Ropeless (On-Demand) pot/trap systems are designed to be deployed without surface buoy lines in the water column and therefore nearly entirely reduce the risk of entanglement for ETP			✓			✓			

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE					BYCATCH SPECIES			
		 Seabirds								
	species. Most of these systems utilise an acoustic release device that can be activated from the boat which will either release a buoy line or inflate a float bag attached to the pots/traps in the water. The pots/traps can then be retrieved by fishers.									
Sharkguard	Longline fisheries set out a long main line with hundreds to thousands of baited hooks attached on branch lines. Sharks and rays are attracted to baited hooks in addition to target species resulting in tens of millions caught as bycatch in longline fisheries each year.		✓					✓		
Smart Buoys	Smart buoys provide constant location information so that gear can be tracked remotely, which helps fishers locate gear if it has come loose or moved in a storm. Importantly, it also can alert fishers when buoy lines are being dragged, for example provide continuous real-time location data of entangled whales which would greatly increase disentanglement success.	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
Streamer (tori) lines	Streamer lines, also called tori or bird scaring lines, deter birds from sinking baits, dramatically reducing seabird attacks and related mortalities. Runs from a high point at the stern to a device or mechanism that creates drag at its terminus. Brightly coloured streamers hanging from the aerial extent of the line scare birds from flying to and under the line, preventing them from reaching the baited hooks, becoming hooked and subsequently killed.		✓		✓				✓	
Sub-Surface Sets	Surface set gillnets can catch sea turtles and small cetaceans that spend most of their time at the surface. By increasing the depth of the float line (the top rope on the net) a few meters, sea turtles and small cetaceans at the surface can pass over without becoming entangled, decreasing the bycatch rate.	✓					✓	✓	✓	

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE					BYCATCH SPECIES			
		 Seabirds								
Weak Inserts, Weak Rope	Pots and traps fisheries use buoy lines (high-strength ropes) attached to pots and traps to mark gear on the ocean bottom. Buoy lines that extend from the trap on the seafloor to the surface sometimes cause marine mammals and sea turtles to become entangled often leading to severe injury or death.			✓			✓			
Weighted Branchline	Weighted branch lines increase the sink rate of baited hooks decreasing the amount of time that they can be predated on by seabirds and that seabirds can get hooked.		✓						✓	

Source of data: Bycatch Solutions Hub (<https://bycatchsolutions.org/solutions/?keyword=&active-filter=ocean&ocean=northern-atlantic-ocean>); Bycatch Management Information System (<https://www.bmis-bycatch.org/mitigation-techniques>); FAO (Marine mammal bycatch mitigation, <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/bycatch-mitigation-mammals/search>); ACAP (<https://www.acap.aq/bycatch-mitigation/mitigation-advice>); SPEA (https://www.spea.pt/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Factsheetsx3_FINAL.pdf)

Source of fishing gear and species icons: Bycatch Solutions Hub (<https://bycatchsolutions.org/solutions/?keyword=&active-filter=ocean&ocean=northern-atlantic-ocean>)